

**INFLUENCE OF SENSITIZATION OF ENGLISH TEACHERS
TOWARDS INTERNAL INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISION ON
THEIR TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS
IN KAKAMEGA COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

Instructional supervision is key to effective teaching. Whereas emphasis has been put on external instructional supervision, less attention has been given to Internal Instructional Supervision (IIS), probably because its influence on teaching effectiveness is yet to be established. Kakamega County is the second largest County in terms of population yet achievement in English is low at a mean score of 5.28 in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Examination (2007-2012). The County's Panel of Standards Assessment report, 2010 and 2011 pegged this to weak IIS structures. The purpose of this study was to establish influence of sensitization of teachers of English towards IIS on their teaching effectiveness. A conceptual framework constituting of sensitization of teachers of English towards internal instructional supervision as the independent variables and teaching effectiveness as the dependent variable was used. The study used *ex-post facto*, correlation and descriptive survey. Population was 13 Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (QUASO), 247 principals, 247 HODs and 494 English Teachers (ET). It sampled 13 QUASO, 74 principals, 74 HODs and 215 teachers purposively. Questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis guide were used. To establish validity, the instruments were given to experts in language pedagogy. A pilot study was conducted using 10% of the population; hence, 24 principals, 24 HODs and 50 teachers were used to establish reliability. Quantitative data was analysed using frequencies, percentages and Pearson's correlation coefficient and

regression. Qualitative data was transcribed, categorized and reported in themes relevant to the study. Findings revealed that teachers of English had been greatly sensitized on professional documents but least sensitized on purpose of IIS and they were rarely sensitized on matters of IIS through in-service. The study concludes that sensitization of ET towards IIS is not a significant factor of predicting teaching effectiveness and only 10.4 % of teaching effectiveness can be predicted by sensitization of ET towards IIS. The study thus recommends that stakeholders of IIS should sensitize teachers of English on the purpose of IIS, frequency of conducting IIS, teacher preparedness towards IIS and exposure through in-service since these are positively significant to teaching effectiveness.

Keywords: internal instructional supervision, influence, teaching effectiveness, sensitization

1. Background of the Study

One of the challenges facing education systems in most countries world over is how to uphold quality of public education amidst the increasing national and fiscal constraints. In 2009, Polish's Ministry of Education (MOE) requested the World Bank's assistance in exploring ways to improve teaching quality and education outcomes through improved systems of supervision and support to schools (Nakpodia, 2006). According to international literature, many teachers may not have mastered sufficient skills for effective teaching; hence, there is need for instructional supervision (Beach & Reinhartz, 2000). Through this supervision, Eneastor (2001) propounds that, they acquire new teaching skills, classroom management skills and positive attitude towards instruction.

In Africa just as in the international perspective, quality in education is equally prioritized. Nakpodia (2006) emphasized that particular attention should be given to the issues concerning education quality and improvement strategy in the developing world. He further mentioned that there is substantial evidence of decline in education quality in many developing countries even at a time when donor assistance has been directed towards education improvement. Basing on this state of affairs, it is thus possible that various educational aspects that promote quality are at stake, of particular interest to this study is internal instructional supervision.

Findings of many studies conducted in Africa including studies by, Alimi and Akinflorin, (2012), Kipkurui (2012) Odu and Udu (2016), Orenaiya *et al* (2014) Thembinkosi (2013) have supported the fact that effective supervision results to achieving the stated goals of education. Thus, when matters that pertain to IIS are put under perspective then this declining quality in education in Africa can be remedied.

Since 1963, the government of Kenya has made significant strides in providing quality education to its citizens. None the less, The MOE report on the Sector Review and Development (2003) pointed out the problem of quality of teaching and learning in various secondary schools. This was attributed to teacher inadequacy, ineffectiveness

and motivation. The report then recommended that supervision of instruction should be used to offer instructional improvement within the education system. In Kakamega County, the performance of English is wanting. The average mean score in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) for the years 2007-2012 was 5.26 an equivalent of C-. The secondary schools' inspection reports of 2010 and 2011 by the County Standards Assessment Panel of secondary schools in the County revealed that the overall performance of subjects is low as quality grades are missing. The weakness that this team pointed out, directly touched on issues concerning internal instructional supervision and monitoring of the curriculum implementation in most schools. Such aspects included poor syllabus coverage; inadequate internal supervision and monitoring of the curriculum implementation in most schools; most of the heads of department assessed in these schools were not effective in curriculum supervision in their departments and there were also cases of teacher absenteeism reported.

There is therefore need to focus on teachers. Odo and Udu (2016) underscore the importance of teachers by opining that teachers occupy (and of course will always occupy) a prominent position in the teaching and learning process. They are as a matter of fact, the bedrock upon which this process rests. This has the implication that when teachers are sharpened in terms of enhancing their effectiveness then out rightly the goals of education are upheld.

There are numerous ways of sharpening teachers in terms of their productivity and effectiveness. This study contends that supervision surfaces as an important tool to be used to equip teachers. Supervision is not merely about the act of teachers instructing or teaching students but also the action that enables teachers to improve instruction for students (Glickman *et al*, 2004 & Wanzare, 2011). It is the process through which principals (deputy principals and HODS attempt to work with teachers collaboratively to improve teaching and learning in the school (Wanzare, 2011). This implies that through IIS students' achievement is enhanced. When the teachers' delivery of instruction is put under the spot light their attention towards students' academic welfare is heightened. This is reiterated when Sergiovanni and Starrat (2006) reinstate that when a school's instructional capacity improves teaching improves, leading to improvement in students' performance.

Improved instruction implies that teaching is effective since teachers will attain better results. Osae (2012) observes that supervision aims at facilitating learning through planning and devising ways of improving teachers professionally and releasing their creative abilities and talents so that they willingly improve the learning situation. Ryan (2004) adds that supervision is an enquiry into practice. Practice here implies the act of teaching. Osae (2012) further qualifies that this ought to be a compassionate appreciative enquiry.

There is therefore need to improve upon the quality of teaching in secondary schools through effective internal supervision of teachers. One of the major causes of the poor academic performance can be ineffective (internal) instructional supervision (Alimi & Akinfolarin, 2012). As a result of this IIS must be made a priority.

Thembinkosi (2013) contends that it is generally believed that if teachers are left on their own they may not try to develop their teaching skills. The main objective of supervisory practice in schools is to improve instruction, which is, teaching and learning. According to Pearson, (2009), when supervising in the educational realm, supervisors should seek to help those being supervised realize their possibilities and usefulness.

Sergiovanni and Starrat (2006) further clarify that instructional supervision is an opportunity accorded to teachers to develop their capacities towards contributing towards and for students' academic success. It is therefore, an essential activity for the effective operation of a good school system. There is therefore need to strengthen schools instructional supervision so as to ensure that teacher high productivity and work commitment is guaranteed and enhanced as proposed by Ikegbusi (2014). Supervisors need to get out of their way and organize for workshops, seminars and conferences on IIS so as to expose teachers to this practice as well as build their capacities.

Various researchers have recommended on the need to sensitize teachers generally through in-service on a regular basis (Indoshi, 1999, Odu & Udu 2016, Okwach 2009, 2016 and Wanzare, 2011). This is because when teachers are exposed to workshops, seminars and conferences on IIS then their teaching capacities are stepped up. There was therefore need to find out whether these recommendations have been acted upon in as far as IIS is concerned in the teaching of English in Kakamega County. In addition, sensitization may as well be facilitated by principals and HODs right within the school setup. This is by these supervisors educating teachers on the purpose, objectives, documents, organization, frequency and type of IIS. This rests on the strength that they have closer interactions with teachers than other stakeholders of supervision.

Wanzare and Ward (2000) point out that the Kenyan government, in an attempt to ensure quality teaching in schools, has invested substantial amounts of financial and human resources directed toward science training programs for teachers. However, there is need to equally invest in the languages and more so in English subject. This is because English is an official language and most official duties are transacted in English. If learners are well equipped in the subject, the entire nation stands to benefit.

In addition, Rotumoi (2006) suggested that there was need for Kenya Institute of Education (KIE) currently known as Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (K.I.C.D) and the Ministry of Education in Kenya to organize frequent seminars and workshops and in- service courses for teachers on a regular basis to enlighten, update and expose them to matters of IIS such as its frequency, type to be used and how they can have a positive attitude towards it.

Similarly, Indoshi (1999) observed that in-service Education and Training (INSET) is important for the improvement of teachers' competence and that all teachers should be provided with opportunity to attend it. In this context, INSET of teachers can simply be defined as continuing professional development of teachers.

Okwach (2009) further clarifies that in relation to 1975 recommendations of International Conference on education by UNESCO recommendation number 19 states that continuing education should be an integral part of the teacher education process and should therefore be arranged on a regular basis for all categories of education personnel. Procedures should be as flexible as possible and adoptable to teacher individual needs and to the special features of each region, taking into account developments in different specialties and the extensions of knowledge. Thus this study set to find out whether Indoshi (1999) and Okwach (2009)'s recommendations have been worked upon in the teaching of English and whether this has any influence on teaching effectiveness.

Equally, Kathleen (2006), adds that supervisors should provide for mentoring of beginning teachers through facilitating a supportive induction into the profession and by doing so they improve the incompetent teacher (Olatoye, 2006 & Chike-Okoli, 2006). This is also echoed by Strauss (2005) in his paper entitled: a model of for evaluating South Africa's Education System Based on SACQMEC II Research Data. He states that according to the norms and standards set by the Department of Education a teacher is expected to receive 80 hours (ten eight-hour working days) of in- service training a year which would translate to 30 days in three years (SACMEQ II, 2005).

2. Research Materials

2.1 Research Design

The study used *ex- post- facto*, correlation and descriptive survey.

2.2 Target Population

Population included 13 Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (QUASO), 247 principals, 247 HODs and 494 teachers.

2.3 Sample Size and Sampling procedure

It sampled 13 QUASO, 74 principals, 74 HODs and 215 teachers purposively.

2.4 Data Collection instruments

Data for this study was collected by use of questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis

3. Sensitization of English Teachers towards Internal Instructional Supervision

This study sought to find out the extent to which teachers of English had been sensitised towards certain variables of IIS. The results of this response are depicted below in Table 1.

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Table 1: Report of ET on their Sensitization towards IIS

Statements on Sensitization	N	Very Large Extent	Large Extent	Not Sure	Small Extent	Very Small Extent	Mean
		5 <i>f%</i>	4 <i>f%</i>	3 <i>f%</i>	2 <i>f%</i>	1 <i>f%</i>	
Understanding Purpose of IIS	215	36 16.7	99 46	15 7	49 22.8	16 7.5	2.29
Outlining objectives clearly	215	34 15.8	109 50.7	14 6.5	40 18.6	18 4.1	3.47
Awareness of aspects	215	73 34	84 39.1	19 8.8	25 11.6	12 5.6	3.82
Awareness of documents	215	97 45.5	71 33	10 4.7	25 11.6	12 5.6	4.01
Awareness of frequency of IIS	215	42 19.5	98 45.6	30 14	24 11.2	21 9.8	3.66
Awareness of teacher preparedness	215	59 27.4	91 42.4	19 8.8	25 11.6	21 9.8	3.66
Awareness of type of supervision	215	42 19.5	98 45.6	30 14	24 11.2	21 9.8	3.54
Awareness of modalities of feedback	215	32 14.9	87 40.5	30 14	37 17.2	29 13.4	3.26
Sensitization through in-service	215	27 12.6	68 31.6	14 6.5	40 18.6	66 30.7	2.77
Total average mean score							3.22

Source: Field data

Table 1 shows E T response on the extent of sensitization of certain specified aspects of IIS. Results reveal that respondents termed their sensitization towards understanding of purpose of IIS, clear outline of objectives of IIS, awareness of aspects to be observed during IIS classroom observation, awareness of frequency of conducting IIS, awareness of teacher preparedness, type of supervision to be used and modalities of receiving feedback to be to a fair extent. They all termed their sensitization towards documents used in IIS to be to a great extent. Results also reveal that the response of these respondents particularly that of the teachers themselves on the extent of sensitization through in-service was to a little extent. The overall mean for all the aspects of extent of sensitization for principals, HODs and ET was 3.68, 3.58 and 3.22 respectively.

Interview schedules with principals revealed that teachers are sensitized on IIS through various fora. These included seminars and workshops, staff meetings and staff briefs as well as departmental meetings. Other principals confirmed that newly deployed teachers and those on teaching practice are sensitized on IIS through meetings in the principal's office, a kind of one to one sensitization. In addition, interview schedules with QASOs also confirmed that there were sensitization seminars that were organized occasionally by the Ministry of Education for ET to be equipped with information on curriculum implementation as deemed important.

These results are in line with those of Nyagua and Reeca (1999) who found that in- service was rare. They found out that head teachers in Zimbabwe put little effort on staff development activities for teachers. These results imply that the respondents are well aware of the documents that are used in IIS. This could be due to the fact that they handle these documents on a daily basis since most of those documents require being

updated. These results also imply that respondents are fairly aware of other aspects of IIS such as its purpose, frequency, objectives, teacher preparedness, type and modalities of receiving feedback.

It is also clear from these results that little sensitization in form of in- service has been done. This could be due to limited resources, lack of awareness by its stakeholders about its significance to teachers mean scores or simply a carefree attitude. With such a state of affairs then the influence of sensitization of teachers of English on IIS may not bare much fruit. This will then result to ineffectiveness in teaching.

2. Teaching Effectiveness of English Teachers

Teaching effectiveness refers to individual teachers' 2013 KCSE examination mean scores. Any mean score below 4.99 implied low teaching effectiveness, those between 5.00- 6.99 was fair teaching effectiveness, those between 7.00- 8.99 implied good teaching effectiveness while all those above 9.00 reflected excellent teaching effectiveness. This is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Teaching Effectiveness

Mean Score Range	<i>f</i>	Percentage
2.5 - 4.99	89	39.72
5.00 - 5.99	45	21.02
6.00 - 6.99	29	13.55
7.00 - 7.99	20	9.35
8.00 - 8.99	24	11.22
9.00 - 9.99	11	5.14
10.00. - 10.99	-	-
11.00 - 12.00	-	-
Total	214	100

Results of Table 2 show that 60.74 % of teachers of English have fair and low teaching effectiveness, only 20.57% of them had good teaching effectiveness and only 5.14% of them had excellent teaching effectiveness. This implies that there is therefore something amiss in the performance of this subject which could sprout from teaching ineffectiveness which is as a result of weak IIS structures, particularly with reference on sensitization of ET towards IIS.

3. Influence of Sensitization of ET towards IIS

It was important to establish the influence of sensitization of ET towards IIS on their teaching effectiveness. Table 3 below shows this association.

Table 3: Sensitization towards IIS as a Predictor of Teaching Effectiveness

R	RR	Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
	.378 ^a	.143	.104	1.067	Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
					.104	3.709	9	209	.000 ^a

Source: SPSS processing

The results generated from the data show:

- a) Predictors (constant), awareness of documents, objectives clearly outlined, awareness of aspects of IIS, awareness of frequency of IIS, teacher preparedness, awareness of type of IIS, awareness of modalities of feedback, ET personally attending in-service
- b) Dependent variable: Teachers' means scores in 2013 KCSE

The results of Table 3 suggest that awareness of aspects of IIS is not a significant predictor ($R^2= 0.104$, $F(9,209) = 3.709$, $p=0.000 < 0.005$) of teaching effectiveness. It is only 0.104(10.4%) of teaching effectiveness that can be predicted by the awareness of aspects of IIS.

Regression analyses were further used to test which of the predictors contributed most to professional development. Table 4 shows these results.

Table 4: The Regression Model of Predicting Teaching Effectiveness using Sensitization of TE towards IIS

Aspect of IIS	B	SEB	βp	Value
Model intercept	2.935	.222	-	.000
Understanding purpose of IIS	.086	.097	.093	.376
Objectives of IIS spelt out	-.148	.097	-.158	.127
Awareness of aspects checked	-.182	.095	-.196	.056
Awareness of documents	-.014	.087	-.015	.877
Awareness of frequency of IIS	-.103	.089	.109	.250
Teacher preparedness	.078	.088	.088	.375
Awareness of type of IIS	-.119	.101	-.134	.242
Awareness of mode of feedback	-.195	.105	-.222	.065
Sensitization through in- service	.008	.062	.010	.899

Results in Table 4 indicated that at the standardized β we can observe that a weak but significant positive relationship is found for four of the predictors: understanding of purpose of IIS ($\beta .097$), awareness of frequency of IIS ($\beta .109$), teacher preparedness ($\beta .088$) and ET personally attending in-service ($\beta .010$). Thus understanding the purpose of IIS, awareness of frequency of IIS, teacher preparedness and ET personally attending in-service are contributing more towards teaching effectiveness than the rest of the variables. However, none of these four aspects show a significant positive relationship with teaching effectiveness in English and thus are not significantly related to teaching effectiveness.

4. Conclusion

This study concludes that ET have been greatly sensitized on professional documents but least sensitized on purpose of IIS and they are rarely sensitized on matters of IIS through in-service.

5. Recommendations

1. The study established that teachers are more sensitized towards professional documents than purpose of IIS and they are rarely sensitized through in- service which are positively related to teaching effectiveness. As a result of this study recommends that
2. Principals, deputy principals and HODs should create fora within the school which will be used as avenues of sensitizing teachers of English towards IIS.
3. Quality Assurance and Standards Officers should organize for workshops and seminars for sensitizing teachers' of English towards IIS.
4. The Ministry of Education should organize for in- service courses on IIS for teachers of English and also furnish schools with funds for strengthening IIS.
5. The Ministry of Education should also organize in-service courses for internal instructional supervisors so as to equip them with supervisory skills such as tact and interpersonal nuggets to ensure the teachers of English are motivated towards a better and more productive teaching rather than fault finding, coach them on significance of IIS, impress upon them the need for observing guidelines of frequency of IIS and the need to greatly sensitize their teachers on IIS through in- service.

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